

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D5.2 STAKEHOLDER LIAISON WITH RELEVANT INITIATIVES

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 5.2 - Stakeholder Liaison with Relevant Initiatives highlights interregional initiatives involving stakeholders from the three pilot regions (Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia), as well as stakeholders at the international level. It is closely connected to *Deliverable 4.4 - Report on Coordination Actions with Key Related Initiatives*, which quantifies stakeholder involvement in INTEGER regional events. Additionally, insights from national and international events are integrated into a comparative analysis in *Deliverable 5.3 - Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholders' Implementation Report*.

The deliverable introduces its purpose, synergies with other tasks and deliverables, and the goals of this task within WP5 (**Chapter 1**). It outlines the methodology (**Chapter 2**), detailing activities to promote stakeholder liaison and analysing participant data provided by the partners responsible for organising the initiative. This analysis examines stakeholder involvement across the quadruple helix, their positioning on the Power-Interest Grid (as defined in Deliverable 5.1), and their levels of engagement.

Stakeholder liaison activities (**Chapter 3**) are organised into five project phases: identifying challenges, consulting on the 4H model, engaging key players in the Col-laboratory, training and incubating, and celebrating milestones. Each phase includes a summary of planned events (and descriptions of the activities not covered in other deliverables), participant analyses, and lessons learned.

A summary of participating organisations and their engagement levels (**Chapter 4**) provides an overview of all organisations involved, including a breakdown by helix and engagement levels. The deliverable concludes (**Chapter 5**) with key lessons learned and reflections.

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Table 1 - Symbols, abbreviations, and acronyms

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T	Task
WP	Work-Package
i2CAT	FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL A CATALUNYA
URV	UNIVERSITAT ROVIRA I VIRGILI
FURV	FUNDACIO URV
F6S	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED
HAM	BEHOERDE FUER ARBEIT, GESUNDHEIT, SOZIALES, FAMILIE UND INTEGRATION HAMBURG
UJ	UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI
KTP	KRAKOWSKI PARK TECHNOLOGICZNY SP ZOO
SHINE	SHINE 2EUROPE LDA
AFE	AFEDEMY, ACADEMY ON AGE-FRIENDLY ENVIRONMENTS IN EUROPE BV
E&O plan	Engagement and outreach plan
3 H	Triple Helix
4 H	Fourth Helix
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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

Focused on challenge-driven promotion of healthy living and wellbeing, INTEGER aimed to bring forward three important innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive, and integrative European Union (EU) innovation ecosystems:

- The INTEGER 4 Helix Col-laboratory model to implement the next generation of living labs, the ‘Col-laboratories’,
- An EU Healthy Living Col-laboratory, a true network of networks’ community with capacity to work on real social, tech and business-driven projects, and
- A new professional profile, the ‘col-laber’ or ‘col-laboratory manager’ as a multiplying agent of change of these integrated innovation ecosystems.

The three INTEGER reinforcing innovations aimed to multiply capacities for the integration of social innovation in EU innovation ecosystems:

- Boost win-win games between business and social oriented innovations addressing common challenges.
- Transform co-creation dynamics into disruptive and tangible new products, services or competencies.
- Co-design jointly public innovation policies.
- Develop capacity building of the new generation of socio-digital entrepreneurs and ecosystems’ enablers, the ‘col-labers’, and
- Devise funding and investment mechanisms for social innovation start-ups and SMEs to develop and scale up game changing innovations.

‘Col-laboratories’ and ‘col-labers’ aim to embrace economic and social-driven innovation communities across the EU. INTEGER took a collaborative approach, connecting business-driven methods with social innovation tailored to identified needs. The goal was to accelerate transformative outcomes by fostering win-win collaborations, local synergies, and effective coordination of actions. This included improved governance, implementation, adoption, and long-term impact.

The INTEGER project ran for 2 years, from February 2023 to January 2025, and was organised into 5 work packages.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable begins by introducing its purpose, highlighting synergies with other tasks and deliverables, and summarising the goals associated with this task within WP5 (**Chapter 1 – Introduction**).

The methodology (**Chapter 2**) is then presented, detailing the activities undertaken to promote stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives across various phases. It includes an explanation of how data provided by partners from the regional ecosystems of Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia was collected and analysed. This analysis examines the number of stakeholders involved from the quadruple helix, their positioning on the Power-Interest Grid (as defined in

Deliverable 5.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholders’ Engagement Plan), and their level of engagement.

Following this, the deliverable delves into **stakeholder liaison with relevant activities (Chapter 3)**, structured around five project phases: 1) Identifying challenges and needs; 2) Consulting on the 4H model; 3) Engaging key players in the Col-laboratory events; 4) Acceleration process: training and incubating; 5) Milestones tracking and project sustainability actions. For each phase, a summary of the planned events is provided, along with detailed descriptions for those not covered in other deliverables. The chapter also includes an analysis of participants and organisations, as well as insights and lessons learned to inform future efforts.

A **summary of participating organisations and their engagement levels (Chapter 4)** is then provided, offering a comprehensive overview of all organisations involved in the interregional initiatives. This includes a breakdown of organisations by helix and an assessment of their engagement levels.

The deliverable concludes (**Chapter 5 - Conclusion**) with an analysis of the results presented in the previous sections, providing key takeaways and reflections. Additionally, **appendices** are included to provide further details and supporting documentation.

1.3 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

This deliverable focuses on stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives at interregional and international levels. In contrast, *Deliverable 4.4 – Report on Coordination Actions with Key Related Initiatives* addresses activities conducted at the regional level. Additionally, *Deliverable 5.3 – Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholders’ Implementation Report* provides a comparative analysis, incorporating insights from both national and international events.

As part of WP5, which is transversal to the entire project (see Figure 1), this deliverable provides a summary of previously conducted activities at the interregional and international level. It also includes two additional events not covered in other deliverables: webinar with sister projects and the Final General Assembly. It analyses the stakeholders involved, identifying their respective helix and level of engagement.

Figure 1 - Pert Diagram of INTEGRER

Consequently, it is strongly connected to several other deliverables due to its comprehensive reporting on activities.

This deliverable is closely linked to *Deliverable 2.2 – Collaborathon Report & Exploitation Plan* [1], as it builds on early project events aimed at identifying challenges and needs, involving stakeholders from the three pilot regions as well as international participants.

It is further connected to *Deliverables 4.1 – First Draft of Comprehensive 3H & 4H Integration Innovation Ecosystems Model* [2] and *4.3 – INTEGER 4H Collaboratory Comprehensive Model: Academic Papers Accepted in Scientific Publications* [3], since stakeholders from the pilot regions contributed to the co-creation of the 4H model.

Moreover, it aligns with *Deliverable 4.2 – EU-wide INTEGER Innovative Community Constituted* [4], which reports the signing of the Terms of Reference (ToR). This marked the official launch of the EU Collaboratory and involved stakeholders from the pilot regions, other countries, and European networks.

Finally, it is connected to *Deliverable 3.4 – Collaborathons Final Reports* [5], which includes interregional collaborathons involving the three pilot regions, and *Deliverable 3.5 – Training and Circulating Activities Report* [6], which summarises three training events that engaged numerous international stakeholders.

2. METHODOLOGY

This deliverable provides a systemic analysis of stakeholder engagement strategies within the INTEGER project, focusing on international initiatives. Adopting a systemic perspective, as defined by Systemic design Labs [7] - “approaching a task from a holistic perspective, zooming out of a system to reveal its structure and connections between its parts, and zooming in on the hub of influence that matters most” - we aim to analyse stakeholder engagement across different project phases.

The project encompasses the following phases, each with distinct objectives and stakeholder involvement (see Figure 2):

- Identifying challenges and needs
- Consulting on the 4H Model
- Engaging key players in the Col.laboratory events
- Acceleration process: training and incubation
- Milestones tracking and project sustainability actions

Most events, except for the TOR signature and the Final INTEGER General Assembly (both held in person in Barcelona), have been conducted online or in a hybrid format. This approach was driven by the interregional and international nature of the events, as it involved stakeholders from various parts of Europe.

Figure 2 – INTEGER initiatives that involved engagement between international stakeholders

For each phase, the following items are presented:

- **Brief overview:** Summary of the event(s) planned for each phase, with more detailed descriptions provided for those not covered in other deliverables.
- **Participants and organisations:** Detailed description and analysis of attendees and participating organisations.

- **Results and lessons learned:** Insights and outcomes to refine and enhance future engagement efforts.

To define participants and organisations, **stakeholders were classified by partners using the quadruple helix model**, which identifies four key areas of innovation within innovation ecosystems: Academia, Industry, Civil Society, and Government. Depending on the stakeholder type, they are affiliated with one of these four helixes. The operationalisation is detailed in the table below, which references the stakeholder categories outlined from *Deliverable 5.1*:

Table 2 - Definition of stakeholder types categorised by helix

Helix	Stakeholder type	Definition
Academia	Universities	Higher education institutions that provide academic training, conduct research, and foster innovation while collaborating with public and private sectors to address societal challenges.
	Other research organisations	Institutions dedicated to advancing knowledge through scientific studies, innovation, and the dissemination of research findings, often collaborating with academia, industry, and governments.
Industry	Technology providers	Companies or organisations that develop, deliver, and maintain technological solutions, tools, or platforms for various applications.
	Business actors	Entrepreneurs, companies, or stakeholders involved in economic activities, contributing to market development and job creation.
Civil society	Citizens, NGOs and non-formal active groups	Individuals and community organisations advocating for change, supporting local initiatives, and contributing to societal progress through grassroots efforts.
	Social innovators	Individuals or organisations developing creative solutions to social problems, aiming to improve well-being and drive positive societal change.
Government	Regulatory bodies	Organisations responsible for creating and enforcing rules and standards to ensure compliance within specific industries or sectors.
	Public authorities	Governmental entities at various levels that manage public resources, deliver services, and ensure societal well-being.
	Policy-makers	Individuals or groups responsible for developing policies and strategies to address societal challenges and guide public and private actions.
	International networks	Cross-border alliances or coalitions fostering collaboration, knowledge exchange, and coordinated action among diverse stakeholders.

In addition, the **level of engagement for each organisation** was quantified based on the number of interregional events they attended. While this analysis may not capture other critical forms of engagement, such as informal meetings or regional events - which are undeniably important - it provides insights into identifying the most actively engaged stakeholders throughout the

project. This approach aims to inform and refine future engagement processes, recognising that effective stakeholder engagement involves open communication, active involvement, and relationship building [8].

Stakeholder engagement is categorised as follows:

Table 3 - Definition of engagement levels

Level of engagement	Definition
High	Stakeholders are deeply engaged, actively collaborating, co-creating solutions, or playing a central role in decision-making or implementation processes.
Medium	Stakeholders have been moderately involved, providing occasional feedback, participating in discussions, or contributing to specific aspects of the project.
Low	Stakeholders have been minimally involved, primarily through one-way communication (e.g., receiving project updates, newsletters, or attending events without active participation).

Considering that a total of 13 events is included in this analysis, engagement levels were categorised as follows: **low engagement** for participation in **1–2 events**, **medium engagement** for **3–7 events**, and **high engagement** for **8–13 events**.

Additionally, based on the classification by helix and stakeholder type, a **Power-Interest Grid** [9] is presented as well to visualise stakeholders' added value for INTEGER, following *Deliverable 5.1*. These grids help determine which stakeholders have the power to influence the project and which partners need to be managed closely or simply kept informed, for example. The Power-Interest Grid is a matrix with quadrants that visualise power on one axis and interest on the other. Organisations have been placed in the grid according to their stakeholder type, as shown in Figure 3 - Power-Interest Grid.

Figure 3 - Power-Interest Grid

3. Stakeholder liaison with relevant initiatives

3.1 Identifying challenges and needs

To involve key stakeholders from the beginning and better support them, the next phases of the project - such as developing the 4H Model and the col·laborathons - include **two events** that were organised to identify challenges and needs [8]: 1) the *Key stakeholder pre-event*; 2) *Innovation 4Healthy Living | Let's Hack Together!*, held across two sessions (see Figure 4). These events also aimed to promote the use of the collaborative INTEGER platform, build a culture of openness, encourage partnerships across sectors, drive social innovation, and strengthen stakeholder engagement across the three regional innovation ecosystems: Hamburg, Krakow and Catalonia.

Stakeholders from all three regions were invited by the INTEGER partners, as key stakeholders, with a diverse representation from their regional ecosystems, to join these interregional events that promoted the sharing of ideas and enabled joint collaborations. Full details about these events are available in *Deliverable 2.2 - Col·laborathon Report & Exploitation Plan* [1].

Figure 4 – Events held during the phase “Identifying challenges and needs”

Brief overview of the INTEGER initial stakeholders’ events

Before the online pre-event, key stakeholders were invited to complete a short Google form to identify a healthy living and well-being challenge in their region. This activity aimed to foster engagement, understand participant profiles (sector and region), and identify the main regional challenges, building on insights gathered during INTEGER partner study visits.

The first **Key stakeholder pre-event** took place on April 18, 2023, involving **39 participants** from Krakow, Catalonia, and Hamburg who discussed the challenges of the INTEGER project and its model implementation. Key challenges identified included: 1) developing the potential of older adults; 2) improving transparency and communication between 4H organisations; 3) aligning actions to enhance the quality of life.

The first session of *Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!* was held on May 17, 2023. This event gathered **23 participants online**, with representatives from the quadruple helix. The session addressed three challenges identified in the pre-event by the Key Stakeholders in representation of their regions and encouraged participants to collaborate in smaller inter-regional and intersectoral groups to analyse the thematic transversally. These groups reflected

on these issues and worked to develop innovative solutions while sharing experiences and best practices.

A follow-up **session** on May 25, 2023, where **18 participants** engaged in thoughtful discussions to share best practices and address key questions. One of the main goals of the second session was to explore solutions to help social innovators bring their ideas to market, addressing challenges faced both at the regional and transnational levels. The use of breakout rooms in session 2 facilitated live discussions, building on the reflections from session 1 and fostering valuable networking opportunities.

Participants and organisations

The stakeholder engagement across INTEGER events demonstrated a diverse and well-balanced representation from the quadruple helix model, with the highest participation from the **industry sector (10 organisations)**, followed by **government (6)**, **academia (3)**, and **civil society (1)**, totalling **20 participating organisations** (see Figure 5 and Table 6 for all details).

Figure 5 - Number of organisations by helix and region for the “Identifying Challenges and Needs” events

The **industry** sector had the strongest presence, featuring technology providers and business actors. **Catalonia** led this participation with **5** organisations, such as Bax & Company and Memima Baby. Hamburg contributed with **2** (Philips and IFB Hamburg), while Kraków was represented by **3** organisations, including Fundacja Internationaler Bund Polska and Cracow Instytut Wspomagania Wychowania.

The **government** sector exclusively involved Catalonian institutions, including regulatory bodies and public authorities. Key participants included the Health Public Agency of Catalonia, which stood out for its active participation in all three events, and the Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú, which engaged in two.

Academia was represented by three research and academic institutions: the University Medical Department Hamburg (Hamburg) and two Catalonian organisations - Living Lab de Salut

d'IrsiCaixa and Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili. Notably, the Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa participated in all three events, while Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili joined two.

Civil society had a more limited presence, represented solely by SeniorLab from Catalonia.

In terms of **regional distribution**, **Catalonia** had the highest representation with **13** organisations, highlighting strong local engagement. Kraków followed with **4** organisations, and **Hamburg** contributed **3**.

Participation frequency across the events varied (see Figure 6). The highest commitment by actively engaging in all **three events** was achieved by **3 Catalonian organisations** - Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa (Academia), Bax & Company (Industry), and the Health Public Agency of Catalonia (Government).

Additionally, **4 Catalonian organisations** participated in **two events**: Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili (Academia), Memima Baby (Industry), and 2 government entities: the Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú and Fundació Salut Empordà - Hospital Figueres. This consistent involvement reflects their sustained interest and ongoing collaboration with INTEGER initiatives.

The majority, however, consisted of **13 organisations** that participated in only one event. This diverse group included stakeholders from academia, industry, civil society, and government sectors. Although their participation was limited, their involvement contributed valuable insights and broadened the scope of discussions and activities.

Figure 6 – Frequency of participation by helix for the “Identifying Challenges and Needs” events

Results and lessons learned

In the case of the breakout groups, predominantly composed of stakeholders from their respective regions, it was observed that the regions sought connections with peers from other sectors within their own ecosystem. This presented a valuable opportunity for networking, exchanging ideas and attaining a new awareness regarding the needs and perspectives of other

regions in Europe. Furthermore, the inter-regional discussions facilitated direct contact between stakeholders from different regions, enabling them to gain insights into alternative realities, viewpoints, best practices, lessons learned, strategies, and tools. This broader perspective enriched their understanding of the well-being and healthy living sector, illustrating the connections between European and regional challenges.

The choices made by stakeholders and the resulting outcomes were highly positive in both cases. They highlighted distinct needs and varying levels of engagement across regions, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the ecosystem for INTEGER partners.

3.2 Consulting on the 4H Model

As previously mentioned, for the co-creation of the 4H INTEGER Model, various initiatives and events were organised, including working sessions, events together with INTEGER partners and key stakeholders, as well as the formation of a Model Core Group on the platform named “Model Core Group”.

This process began in 2023, with two interregional **Model Core Group** sessions, which contributed to the development of the initial version of the model.

In 2024, a first **focus group** was conducted with the INTEGER partners, followed by another with stakeholders from Hamburg and Krakow, and a final one with key stakeholders from Catalonia. As part of this deliverable, a focus was given to the second focus group, where there are actors from different regions involved (see Figure 7). Further details on the national focus group in Catalonia can be found in *Deliverable 4.4 - Report on coordination actions with key related activities*.

Figure 7 - Events held during the phase “Consulting on the 4H Model”

Brief overview

The **Model Core Group** started to discuss the identified features and tentative modules of the Model. In this working group, consortium actors interested in participating were able to exchange insights on the Model to develop it together. Two of these working sessions were held online on June 26 and July 10, 2023, counting **15 and 13 attendees** respectively.

Figure 8 - First online session from the Model Core Group

Regarding the Model Core Group platform section, participants could share documents, insights and the possibility of having a conversation, so that co-creation was collected in the same place for later consultation. More details on *Deliverable 4.1. - First draft of comprehensive 3H & 4H integration innovation ecosystems model* [2].

In Spring 2024, additional online Core Model working sessions were conducted using the model previously defined in the last year, involving participants from all three INTEGER regions.

Figure 9 - The Model Core group on the Glocal.network platform

The focus group on May 27, 2024, involved key stakeholders from Hamburg and Krakow, who reviewed the INTEGER 4H Model and shared new suggestions using the collaborative Mural tool. More details are available in *Deliverable 4.3 - INTEGER 4-H Collaboratory comprehensive model: academic papers accepted in scientific publications* [3].

Figure 10 – Screenshot of the Mural of Focus Group (May 27, 2024)

Participants and organisations

During the interregional sessions, **8 organisations** participated, representing various sectors: **1** from **Academia/Research**, **4** from **Industry**, **2** from **Civil Society**, and **1** from **Government**. Of these, 4 organisations were from Catalonia (all helixes except Government), 3 were from Hamburg (Industry and Government) and 1 from Krakow (Civil society) (Figure 11 and Table 7 for all details).

Figure 11 - Number of organisations by helix and region for the “Consulting on 4H Model” events

The **participation varied** across the sessions. Notably, the Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa (Academia/Research), Bax & Company, and the AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster (Industry/Business) from Catalonia demonstrated consistent engagement, attending all three sessions (see Figure 12). Two organisations, Philips (representing Industry in Hamburg) and Senior Lab (representing Civil Society in Catalonia), attended two events. Meanwhile, three organisations attended only

one session: IFB Hamburg (Industry, Hamburg), HCG (Industry, Catalonia), and Life Science Nord (Government, Hamburg).

Figure 12 - Frequency of participation by helix for the “Consulting on 4H Model” events

Although there was no representation from Civil Society in 1 session (*Model Core Group 2*) and no representation from Government in 2 sessions (*Model Core Group 1 and 2*), all key helixes were ultimately involved in co-creating the INTEGER 4H Model.

Results and lessons learned

Regular engagement from key stakeholders, such as Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa, Bax & Company, and AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster, underscores the importance of consistent involvement in co-creation activities. Maintaining continuity is essential for ensuring consistent progress and achieving meaningful outcomes, such as the 4H Model outlined in *Deliverable 4.3 - INTEGER 4-H Collaboratory comprehensive model: academic papers accepted in scientific publications*. This model will be disseminated through an academic paper and has also been made accessible to the public online via LinkedIn ([here](#)).

The absence of representation from Civil Society and Government in some sessions highlights the need for proactive strategies to ensure all helixes are consistently engaged. Identifying and understanding the reasons behind these gaps is crucial for developing future strategies to enhance commitment and participation across all groups.

Interviews with key stakeholders are being conducted to explore potential explanations and gather insights. Depending on the findings, solutions for the future may include adjusting schedules, implementing targeted outreach efforts, or providing incentives to encourage participation in varied settings.

3.3 Engaging key players in the Col-laboratory events

Two key events were held to engage important stakeholders in the **Col-laboratory** (see Figure 13). The first event was the **Terms of Reference (ToR) Signature** during a conference attended by hundreds of participants. This event served as a platform to formalise commitment and foster collaboration in the first year of the project. The second event was a **webinar with sister projects**, aimed at facilitating the exchange of experiences, challenges, and opportunities. This webinar led to the creation of joint articles between INTEGER and several of these projects, highlighting the collaborative efforts and shared insights.

Figure 13 - Events held during the phase “Engaging key players in the Col-laboratory events”

3.3.1 TOR Signature

Brief overview

The EU INTEGER Col-laboratory was official launched through the official share of a Terms of Reference to be signed, in the The OpenLivingLab Days. This was the stage chosen as this flagship annual event organised by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) took place in September 2023 and attracted over 200 participants, giving INTEGER actions visibility, reaching a wider audience and credibility, in the context of such prestigious and recognised events.

The Terms of Reference document was made available [here](#) (recently updated), to gather signatures and endorsements from stakeholders. Signatures have been collected through, firstly a google form, and updated to an EU Survey, an online survey-management system designed to create and publish globally accessible and GDPR-compliant forms. The survey can be accessed through here: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EUINTEGERCollaboratorySurvey2024> and has been shared at INTEGER initiatives.

The Public Signature of the Terms of Reference (ToR) brought together influential organisations from the 4 Helix, demonstrating their commitment to co-creating innovative solutions for societal challenges and validating our solution. The list of signatories from the OpenLivingLab Days can be found in *Deliverable 4.2 – EU-wide INTEGER Innovative Community Constituted* [4].

Participants and organisations

A total of **52 individuals** and **38 organisations** have signed the Terms of Reference (ToR). These include the signatures of **7 INTEGER partners**, along with **4 individual signatories** who are not affiliated with any specific organisation but have expressed a strong interest in joining the **EU**

Col-laboratory initiative (details in APPENDIX 2: STAKEHOLDERS LISTS BY EVENT / PHASE (Table 8)).

The highest number of signatures comes from the **Academia / Research helix** (16), followed by **Industry** (12), **Government** (7), and **Civil Society** (3) helixes. Specifically, **16 signatories** from the **Academia / Research helix** have committed to the project. These signatories include universities and research organisations from various regions, such as Catalonia, which contributed 4 universities (including 1 INTEGER partner) and 5 other research organisations (with 1 INTEGER partner); 1 university from Krakow (INTEGER partner); and 5 universities from Colombia, Latvia, Turkey, Denmark, and Poland.

The **Industry helix** follows with **12 signatories**, comprising both **technology providers** and **business actors**. Norway Health Tech represents the technology provider from Norway, while business actors are represented across several countries. Catalonia contributes 5 organisations, followed by Krakow (INTEGER partner), and representatives from Lithuania, Romania, Spain, and INTEGER partners from Netherlands, Portugal, and the United Kingdom.

Next, the **Government helix** accounts for **7 signatories**, including public authorities and international networks. Of these, 4 signatories come from Catalonia, including the Catalan Ministry of Health, the Secretary of Telecommunications and Digital Transformation, and other key institutions, demonstrating significant regional governmental support. Additionally, Hamburg is represented by the Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs, and Integration (INTEGER partner), while the European Network of Living Labs and the European School of Social Innovation contribute valuable international network representation.

In the **Civil Society helix**, **3 organisations** have signed, with 2 participants from Catalonia and 1 from Germany.

In addition to the organisational signatories, **4 individuals** from Germany, India, Poland, and the United Kingdom have also expressed their support for the initiative, representing the four sectors of the quadruple helix.

Results and lessons learned

A total of 52 individuals from various sectors, regions, and countries expressed interest in joining the EU Col-laboratory. Within the INTEGER innovation ecosystems, while Catalonia totalled 19 signatures (including 2 INTEGER partners), Krakow had 2 signatures (both INTEGER partners), and Hamburg contributed 1 signature (INTEGER partner).

The lack of signatories from some regions or sectors underscores the need for ongoing engagement and outreach. While regions like Catalonia demonstrate strong institutional support, others, such as Hamburg and Krakow, may require additional efforts to mobilise local stakeholders. The partners' analysis of this situation concluded that that it may be attributed to the maturity level of each regional ecosystem. This is influenced by the strength of pre-existing relationships between i2CAT and key stakeholders, as well as their familiarity with the Co-laboratory concept. The first Col-laboratory, the *Col-laboratori*, was held in 2018 by i2CAT and with the support of the Catalonian Government, which likely contributed to raising awareness of the concept among key stakeholders in the region. This increased familiarity may explain the higher number of signatures from the region and higher engagement along the

INTEGER actions on this regard. This early development has likely fostered greater trust and interest in the concept. Additionally, the requirement for stakeholders to sign a formal document, even when explained to have no repercussions, may be unappealing. It can create hesitation, as stakeholders might be concerned about potential risks or consequences that they do not fully control, even with reassurances.

Despite this, the diversity of interest from individuals demonstrates the broad appeal of the initiative across sectors and geographies.

3.3.2 Webinar

Brief overview

On **16 September 2024**, INTEGER hosted a webinar attended by **32 participants** from **Portugal, Greece, Lithuania, Romania, Norway, Italy, Germany, and Estonia**. This webinar provided a valuable opportunity for participants to engage with a range of innovative projects, including both INTEGER and its sister projects funded under the same Horizon Europe call, as well as related initiatives working in similar domains. The event facilitated discussions on collaboration, synergies, and the potential for joint activities to advance shared objectives in the social innovation and research ecosystems.

Figure 14 - Results from the session with participants by country

The session started with an introduction to the INTEGER project, followed by detailed presentations of the representatives of the following initiatives:

- **CHESS** (*Change Hubs for Ecosystemic Social Solutions*) – Presented by **Dana Cappiello** (Project Ahead) & **Laura Espiau Guarner** (SIX)
- **IBESI** (*Integrated Baltic Ecosystem for Social Innovation*) – Presented by **Mart Veliste** (Baltic Innovation Agency)
- **POSITIVE** (*Participatory Open Social Innovation Through Interlinking Valuable Ecosystems*) – Presented by **Clara Duffner** (Steinbeis Europa Zentrum)
- **Consolid8** (*Consolidating Deep & Inclusive Social Innovation Ecosystems*) – Presented by **Raluca Prelucă** (Fonduri-Structurale.ro)
- **SIRENE** (*Social Innovation Responsive Environments Network*) – Presented by **Miriam Cabrita** (SHINE 2Europe)
- **Invest4Health** (*Mobilizing Novel Finance Models for Health Promotion and Disease Prevention*) – Presented by **Theo Xenakis** (Norway Health Tech)

The flow of presentations and discussions of the event is represented in the **agenda** below:

Table 4 - Webinar agenda

Time	Description of presentation	Speaker (name - organisation)
12h00 - 12h10	Welcome, ice-break activity, recording and presentation of agenda	Inês Saavedra - <i>SHINE 2Europe</i>
First part - INTEGER sister projects and others		
12h10 - 12h20	Introduction to the call and INTEGER project	Rafel Nualart and Fàtima Canseco-Lopez - <i>i2CAT</i>
12h20 - 12h27	CHESS - Change Hubs for Ecosystemic Social Solutions	Dana Cappiello and Marco Traversi - <i>PROJECT AHEAD</i> Laura Espiau Guarner - <i>Social Innovation Exchange</i>
12h27 - 12h34	IBESI - Integrated Baltic Ecosystem for Social Innovation	Mart Veliste and Merey Beisembayev - <i>Baltic Innovation Agency</i>
12h34 - 12h41	POSITIVE - Participatory Open Social Innovation Through Interlinking Valuable Ecosystems	Clara Duffner - <i>Steinbeis Europa Zentrum</i>
12h41 - 12h48	Consolid8 - Consolidating deep & inclusive social innovation ecosystems	Raluca Prelucă - <i>Fonduri Structurale</i>
12h48 - 12h55	SIRENE - Social Innovation Responsive Environments NETWORK	Carina Dantas, Miriam Cabrita - <i>SHINE 2Europe</i>
12h55 - 13h02	Invest4Health - Mobilising novel finance models for health promotion and disease prevention	Theo Xenakis - <i>Norway Health Tech</i>
Second part - How to move forward?		
13h02 - 13h30	Co-creation session	All

Figure 15 - Screenshots of presentations from the webinar

Following the project presentations, a **co-creation session** was held with the prompt: “How can we move forward to identify synergies and explore ways to collaborate and support each other?”. During this session, representatives from the invited projects were encouraged to fill out sections on “Key Results,” “Aspirations,” “Current Challenges,” “What Could You Offer?,” and “What Do You Need?”. This structure allowed all participants, even those not directly associated with the presented projects, to contribute ideas on "Potential Synergies." The insights gathered can be seen in the screenshots from the Mural, below (link [here](#)).

Figure 16 – Collaborative mural with answers from all webinar participants'

Participants and organisations

The **32 participants** in the webinar came from diverse sectors from the "quadruple helix" model, including Academia, Private Sector (including SMEs), and Civil Society. A total of **19 organisations** were involved, with the **industry** sector showing the strongest engagement, contributing **12** organisations. **Academia** (3 organisations) and **civil society** (4 organisations) were also represented, ensuring a balanced participation from diverse stakeholder groups and promoting a well-rounded discussion across various areas of expertise. Further details can be found in Table 9.

In addition to organisations from the INTEGER ecosystems regions and already participated in other project activities, such as IBCH PAS from Krakow, AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster, and ITA - Institut Català d'Antropologia from Catalonia, a wide range of organisations from other countries participated. This included global entities such as Social Innovation Exchange and YourY Network. Furthermore, stakeholders from several European countries contributed to the diversity of the group, including Lithuania (3 organisations), Italy (2), Norway (2), Germany (1), Romania (1), Greece (1), and Estonia (1).

A significant achievement is that all these organisations were first contacted through the project for the webinar, with follow-up actions taking place, such as joint articles and the exchange of resources from projects, including the integration of materials from other sister projects within the INTEGER Learning Network. Additionally, some events were shared with INTEGER partners, contributing to the dissemination efforts of the consortium and marking the beginning of fruitful collaborations.

Results and lessons learned

The **dissemination efforts** were considered essential for attracting a diverse range of participants to the webinar, many of whom INTEGER had not previously engaged with. In this

regard, LinkedIn posts were shared in advance of the event, including one week ([here](#)) and 15 days prior to the webinar ([here](#)), helping to generate interest. Additionally, emails were sent to all participants from the EU Col-laboratory and consortium partners, urging them to share the event within their networks, including relevant groups such as Good Brother and Net4AgeFriendly. A dedicated [news article](#) was also published on the INTEGER website to promote the webinar and provide further details. These efforts contributed to a wider reach and successful engagement, as reflected in Table 9.

The session revealed common challenges across the projects, sparking dynamic discussions on shared resources and collaboration potential. Following the event, all the insights from the co-creation session were compiled into a single document, which provided contributions from both the project representatives and others within the INTEGER consortium (see Appendix II). Additionally, each sister project expressed interest in sharing their presentations on the **INTEGER learning network** ([here](#)).

Figure 17 – Screenshot of the presentations uploaded on the Learning Network on the Glocal platform

Some projects also showed a willingness to collaborate on **joint articles with INTEGER**, focusing on the similarities and differences between the initiatives (more detailed information is provided in *Deliverable 5.3 – Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholders’ Implementation Report*).

An evaluation of the webinar was conducted, and some feedback highlighted areas for improvement. One participant noted that the content of some presentations was difficult to grasp, particularly due to slides being overly detailed with too much information on a single

slide. This participant suggested that, in future webinars, fewer presentations should be given, or that a more specific sub-topic should be addressed to avoid overwhelming the audience with

Figure 18 - Screenshot of the webinar recording

too much content. Despite this, the event led to at least one follow-up meeting between two of the sister projects, and the general feedback was positive overall. The webinar video is available on the resources page on INTEGER [website](#).

3.4 Acceleration process: Training and incubating

During the "Acceleration process: Training and incubating" phase, various interregional activities were organised with the primary aim of accelerating project development. These included the *Interregional Col-laborathon*, the *Col-laber training day*, and two events organised as part of the mentoring process, which were also open to a broader audience: *How to Sell with AI & LinkedIn* and *Communicate: Impact and Transform – The Im-perfect Pitch*. A summary of these sessions is provided below, while comprehensive details can be found in *Deliverable 3.5 - Business Support Intermediate Services Portfolio* [6].

Figure 19 - Events held during the phase "Acceleration process: Training and incubating"

Brief overview

The **Interregional Col-laborathon** was the culmination of the regional events. Held online on January 17, 2024, and with **28 participants**, it brought together the winning projects from each region along with additional stakeholders. The event featured presentations on the outcomes of the regional col-laborathons, an inspirational talk on financing strategies with Josep Biosca of the ShiP2B Foundation, and pitches from the highest-ranked proposals across the regions. The final winner was announced during the event, and the INTEGER team awarded the winner's label and accolades to the finalists underscoring their dedication to fostering development and fundraising support.

Another interregional event was the webinar titled **Col-laber training day** facilitated by AFEdeMy on April 19, 2024, with a total of **43 participants**. The event aimed to strengthen collaboration between different actors within European innovation ecosystems by giving knowledge about the essential fundamentals and skills required for the new position of the Col-laber. Col-labers in the INTEGER project are social innovators with digital skills who can network and boost collaborations within and across regional ecosystems while performing matchmaking activities between social, and business innovators. A main emphasis of the Col-laber is its role as a facilitator, connecting actors from different quadruple helix areas (academia, industry, government, and civil society) to work together more closely. Including presentations from several INTEGER partners, the 4-hour online session transferred valuable insight about digital skills, networking capabilities, and the ability to boost collaborations within and across regional ecosystems. In addition, the training session featured Antonius Schröder from ESSI (European School of Social Innovation) and Laia Pascual from Ship2B as external experts, talking about social innovation and impact investment. To support future involvement of the participants, the Glocal.network platform was presented as a community platform with active individuals from quadruple helix sectors. As a follow-up, the full recording of the training day was uploaded on the INTEGER YouTube channel ([here](#)), while the presented knowledge and skills were also summarised in the Col-laber curriculum, which can be accessed on the INTEGER website ([here](#)).

As part of the broader mentoring process, two additional training sessions were open to all projects and regions involved. The first session, titled **How to Sell with AI & LinkedIn**, was held on 9 May 2024 and led by Inmaculada Vázquez Labella from IVL Consulting in Catalonia. With **41 participants** attending the 1.5-hour session, the training focused on providing actionable insights and skills to enhance the development and success of participating social-digital projects. Attendees learned to utilise artificial intelligence tools to optimise sales strategies and leverage LinkedIn to generate opportunities, expand professional networks, and adopt best practices for digital sales. The session equipped participants with practical tools to advance their sales capabilities and foster professional growth.

The second session, titled **Communicate, Impact, and Transform: The Im-perfect Pitch**, took place on 2 July 2024, featuring Cristina Sáenz de Pipaón from the Institut Català d'Investigació Química (Catalonia) as the speaker. This session, attended by **16 participants**, aimed to enhance communication skills, with a specific focus on crafting impactful pitches. The training helped attendees structure their messages effectively to maintain audience engagement and achieve meaningful impact in their presentations.

Participants and organisations

Across all four events, participation was dynamic and diverse (all details available in Table 10). The **Final Col-laborathon** engaged **28 participants**, the **Col-laber Training Day** attracted **43 participants**, the **How to Sell with AI & LinkedIn** event welcomed **41 participants**, and the **Im-perfect Pitch** involved **16 participants**. This resulted in a total of 128 participant entries, but accounting for two individuals who attended multiple events, the actual number of unique participants was **126**.

The number of participating organisations varied by event, with **8 organisations** attending the **Final Col-laborathon**, **19** at the **Col-laber Training Day**, **22** at the **How to Sell with AI & LinkedIn** session, and **7** at the **Im-perfect Pitch**. In total, **52 unique organisations** participated across the events, accounting for the repeated attendance of Memima Baby (CAT) and Ship2B (CAT) at two events each. These organisations represented four key sectors: **Industry (25)**, **Academia and Research (13)**, **Government (9)**, and **Civil Society (5)**.

Figure 20 - Number of organisations by helix for the “Acceleration process: Training and incubating” events

The **industry sector** had the strongest representation with **25 organisations**. Among these, **20** were from **Catalonia**, including participants such as Memima Baby and Ship2B, along with key players like Bax & Company, Cónorex, and LEITAT Technological Center. Additionally, there were **2** organisations from **Hamburg** (Aufbruch.Hamburg and help Mee Schmerztherapie GmbH), **1** from **Krakow** (Hub4industry), and **2** from **unknown** regions.

The **academia and research sector** also contributed significantly, with **13 organisations** participating. This included **7** from **Catalonia**, such as the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, **1** from **Krakow** (Sano - Centre for Computational Medicine), **3** from **Poland**, including the Medical University of Lodz, **1** from **Norway** (Norwegian University of Science and Technology), and **1** from an **unknown** region.

The **civil society sector** had a total of **5 organisations**, though none participated in the interregional Col·laborathon. This included **4** organisations from **Catalonia**, such as ITA Antropologia and Senior Lab, and **1** from **Krakow**, represented by Fundacja Brata Alberta.

The **government sector**, encompassing both regulatory bodies and public authorities, accounted for **9 organisations**. The regulatory body represented was EureCat Hub FoodTEch, from Catalonia. Public authorities included **2** organisations from **Hamburg** - the Hamburgische Investitions- und Förderbank Hamburg and BWI HH; **3** from **Catalonia** - the Ajuntament de Viladecans, the Consorci Sanitari de Terrassa, and the Clúster TIC Sud; and **2** from **Krakow** - the Małopolska Regional Development Agency UMWM and KLSK (Fundacja Klaster LifeScience Kraków). Additionally, the participation of one **international network**, the European School of Social Innovation, further enriched the diversity and collaborative spirit of the events.

The participation **across the four events** demonstrated **diverse engagement from various sectors** (see Figure 21). Industry consistently showed the highest level of involvement (with exception on the Col·labor training day), particularly during the *How to Sell with AI & LinkedIn* event. Academia was notably active in the *Col·labor Training Day* but had lower representation in other sessions. Government organisations participated in the first three events but were absent from the *Im-perfect Pitch*. Civil society had limited but focused engagement, with the most involvement in the *How to Sell with AI & LinkedIn* event.

Figure 21 - Number of organisations by helix and event for the “Acceleration process: Training and incubating” events

Results and lessons learned

The INTEGER training and incubation events were very successful, bringing together stakeholders from the pilot regions of Krakow, Catalonia and Hamburg. Feedback from the Col.laber training day, collected via Mentimeter, showed a high level of satisfaction and interest in the topics covered. Similarly, the first and second incubation training sessions were praised for their well-organised structure, relevance and engaging delivery through the respective experts. With the wish for future activities, knowledge on areas such as business model development, Social Return on investment, and the effective use of social networks to promote social innovation was particularly appreciated.

While the duration was appropriate for many participants, some suggested that additional time would have been beneficial to delve deeper into the topics and include more practical dynamics, such as examples with videos, interactive exercises, and concrete cases. The high level of motivation shown by participants during the sessions proved a strong interest in fostering deeper collaboration and cross-sectoral cooperation between the 4H stakeholders. However, communication beyond the events showed room for improvement, as engagement within theglocal.network remained limited. As a lesson learned, it will be important to plan enough time in future sessions for more practical collaboration and the registration process to a digital space.

Overall, the events were well received, with participants strongly recommending further development to keep supporting entrepreneurs and professionals. As a follow-up to the training activities and to keep them engaged, all involved stakeholders had been asked to participate in other INTEGER activities like the model review.

3.5 Milestones tracking and project sustainability actions

On November 5-6, the INTEGER project held its final General Assembly in Barcelona, hosted by i2CAT in a hybrid format (see Figure 22). The assembly focused on celebrating achievements, discussing final steps, and exploring ways to sustain its impact. A key element of the assembly was a co-creation session with Catalonian stakeholders and INTEGER partners, designed to guarantee the long-term impact of the project and ensure the practical application of INTEGER’s main results and. Due to its collaborative nature between interregional actors, this session is the focus of study in this deliverable.

Figure 22 - Events held during the phase “Milestones tracking and project sustainability actions”

Brief overview

On November 6, the day concluded with a co-creation session that brought together key stakeholders from the Catalonian ecosystem. The session aimed to raise awareness of INTEGER's updates and the 4H model, serving both as a dissemination effort and as a means to strengthen the relationships built throughout the project. The co-creation session was structured around several questions, such as: "Do any of these results provide added value to you, including training, the methodology for working with the INTEGER 4H Model, and access to networks or platforms?". Additionally, participants discussed the potential benefits and challenges of being part of a community of like-minded individuals. The session also explored what stakeholders would like to see next, both at the regional and interregional levels, ensuring the ongoing relevance and evolution of the project's impact.

Figure 23 - Co-creation part during INTEGER Final General Assembly

Participants and organisations

A total of 30 participants, including INTEGER partners, attended this co-creation session. Beyond the consortium, representatives from **8 external organisations** took part: **3** from **Industry**, **2** from **Civil Society**, **2** from **Government** and **1** from **Academia/Research** (all details in Table 11). While these external participants were based in the Catalonian region - aligned with the face-to-face nature of the event - they actively collaborated with INTEGER partners from other regions, such as Krakow and Hamburg, as well as from other countries, including AFEdeMy (Netherlands) and F6S (United Kingdom). This diverse participation enriched the co-creation process, fostering cross-regional and cross-sectoral collaboration.

The participants invited had varying levels of engagement with the INTEGER project. For example, Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics, L'alzina, Fundació Visible, Ada Navarro, and VHIR were first-time participants, aiming to engage with and join the EU Col-laboratory. This strategic move was intended to involve more key stakeholders and ensure the long-term sustainability of the project.

Suara Cooperative participated in the Catalonian study visit. Two participants, in particular, stand out: Memima Baby not only received mentoring and participated in the Col·labor training day and an additional training session, but was also involved in earlier stages of the project, contributing to key stakeholder pre-event and the one of the sessions of *4Healthy Living | Let's Hack Together!*. Additionally, Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú participated in three other INTEGER events, including two *4Healthy Living | Let's Hack Together!* sessions, and also signed the Terms of Reference (ToR).

Results and lessons learned

The co-creation session between the INTEGER partners and local Catalan stakeholders brought together **three groups** composed of participants from different regions and diverse organisations, representing various helix sectors. This approach ensured a wide range of perspectives and opinions.

Participants were first asked to rate specific outcomes on a scale from 1 to 5, resulting in an average score of 4.25 for access to a network and participatory activities, 4.17 for visibility, 3.83 for active projects around social innovation, 3.75 for the methodology working model, 3.50 for the collaboration platform, and 3.09 for trainings.

Following the ratings, discussions focused on **three key questions**. Regarding the ***potential benefits and challenges of being part of a community of like-minded individuals***, participants highlighted numerous advantages. They emphasised the opportunities to promote new projects, share practices and knowledge within a community united by common goals, and receive invitations to events. The discussions also noted the value of fostering dialogue, providing recommendations, and using a common language to enhance collaboration. Additional benefits included creating connections with venture capital, encouraging interactions between regions, influencing public administration activities, and fostering win-win collaborations. Participants also stressed the importance of identifying potential matches among diverse stakeholders, enabling connections beyond their usual networks.

When reflecting on ***what should come next at the regional level***, participants expressed a desire for tangible outcomes, such as genuine health and social integration. They emphasised the importance of knowledge-sharing through collaboration with local professionals and public administration, creating opportunities for new contacts and partnerships. The vision of an active community that continuously shares information and projects was a common aspiration. Participants also suggested more shared events and the establishment of spaces for collaboration among different actors to foster complementarity.

At the ***interregional level***, participants called for greater collaboration and interaction across regions. Suggestions included sharing events, opening more opportunities for collaboration with the Krakow team, and creating a "hot desk" system to facilitate experience-sharing among organisations. Additionally, they stressed the importance of introducing organisations and initiatives using accessible and straightforward language to enhance inclusivity and understanding.

Figure 24 - Co-creation results from each group

Based on these discussions, it seems that the activities implemented within the INTEGER4H project align well with the interests and objectives of both partners and stakeholders, reinforcing the project's relevance and impact.

4. SUMMARY OF PARTICIPATING ORGANISATIONS AND THEIR ENGAGEMENT LEVELS

It was noted that **13 liaison activities** with stakeholders were conducted at the interregional and/or international level. A summary table detailing the number of participants and organisations per event, as well as per phase as defined at the outset of the deliverable, is provided below in Table 5.

Table 5 - Summary table of each event, including its date, format, number of participants, number of organisations involved, and the deliverables where detailed information can be found, for each project phase.

Event	Date / Format	Number of participants (including INTEGER partners)	Number of organisations (excluding INTEGER partners) ¹	Deliverable details
Identifying challenges and needs				
Key stakeholder pre-event	18.04.2023 Online	39	13	D2.2
Innovation 4Healthy living Let's Hack together! – 1 st session	17.05.2023 Online	23	9	
Let's Hack together! – 2 nd session	25.05.2023 Online	18	7	
Consulting on the 4H Model				
Model Core Group – 1 st session	26.06.2023 Online	15	5	D4.1
Model Core Group – 2 nd session	10.07.2023 Online	13	4	
Focus Group	27.05.2024 Online	16	7	D4.3
Engaging key players in the Col.laboratory				
TOR Signature	21.09.2023 Onsite (Barcelona)	52	38	D4.2
Webinar	16.09.2024 Online	32	19	D5.2
Training and incubating				
Interregional col.laborathon	17.01.2024 Online	28	8	D3.4

¹ An exception was made for the ToR signatures, where signatures from INTEGER partners were included due to the formal commitment and accountability they represent.

Col-laber Training Day	19.04.2024 Online	43	19	D3.5
How to sell with AI & LinkedIn	09.05.2024 Online	41	29	
Communicate, Impact and Transform: The Im-Perfect Pitch	02.07.2024 Online	16	9	
Celebrating milestones and ensuring project sustainability				
INTEGER Final General Assembly	06.11.2024 Onsite (Barcelona)	30	8	D5.2

A total of **118 different organisations** participated in 13 liaison activities with stakeholders at the interregional or international level. Of these, **54** were from the **industry** sector (52 business actors and 2 technology providers), **30** from **academia** (18 universities and 12 other research organizations), **19** from **government** (14 public authorities, 3 regulatory bodies, and 2 international networks), and **15** from **civil society** organisations (see Figure 25).

Figure 25 - Number of organisations by helix involved in the activities conducted within the scope of interregional and international events of the INTEGER project

Of these 118 organisations, **58** are based in **Catalonia** (3 from other regions of Spain), **7** in **Hamburg** (4 from other parts of Germany), and **11** in **Krakow** (4 from other locations in Poland).

Additionally, **7** organisations have **unknown** origins, **2** are **European-wide**, **2** are **global**, and **20** are from **other countries**, including Colombia, Turkey, Latvia, Portugal, Lithuania, Norway, Italy, Romania, and Estonia.

In Figure 26, the **Power-Interest Grid** provides a visual classification of stakeholders involved in the INTEGER project, grouping them based on their influence and level of interest. The analysis reveals that most stakeholders fall into the "**Manage closely**" quadrant, with 54 stakeholders primarily comprising business actors and technology providers. This reflects their active involvement and high level of both interest and power in the project activities.

In the "**Hear their opinions and implement them**" quadrant, 17 stakeholders, including regulatory bodies and public authorities, demonstrate significant power but moderate interest. Their participation ensures that critical insights and decisions are aligned with broader regulatory and administrative frameworks.

30 stakeholders are classified in the "**Monitor with a minimum effort**" quadrant. Despite having limited power and interest, this group - dominated by research organisations and universities - represents valuable contributors with a potential for further engagement. The notable presence of academic and research institutions highlights the project's strong ties to these sectors.

Finally, the "**Keep informed about what the project has decided**" quadrant contains a smaller subset of stakeholders, such as international networks and civil society organisations, who have high interest but limited power. The relatively smaller representation in this quadrant may be attributed to the INTEGER partners' stronger connections with academia and industry.

The full list of stakeholders by quadrant is available in APPENDIX 4: Power-Interest Grid for interregional and/or international activities.

Figure 26 - Power-Interest Grid for interregional and/or international activities (N=118)

Considering the 13 events included in this analysis, the **level of involvement** was categorised based on the frequency of attendance at international and/or interregional events. Specifically, **low engagement** was defined as participation in **1–2 events**, **medium engagement** as participation in **3–7 events**, and **high engagement** as participation in **8–13 events**.

According to these categories, most organisations (**107**) demonstrated **low engagement**, with 92 participating in only *one event* and 15 attending *two events*. **Medium engagement** was less common, with **7** organisations showing more consistent participation. Among these, *three events* were attended by 1 academic organisation from Catalonia (Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili), 1 industry stakeholder from Hamburg (Philips), and one government stakeholder from Catalonia (Health Public Agency of Catalonia, ASPCAT). Participation in *four events* was recorded for 1 government stakeholder (Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú, Catalonia), while *five events* included a civil society organisation (Senior Lab) and an industry stakeholder (AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster), both from Catalonia. Engagement in *six events* involved 1 industry stakeholder (Memima Baby), and attendance at *seven events* was recorded for another industry stakeholder (Bax & Company, Healthy Cities), also from Catalonian region. **High engagement** was rare, with only **1** academic organisation from Catalonia (Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa) participating in eight events (see Figure 27).

Figure 27 – Frequency of attendance at interregional and/or international INTEGER events by organisations, categorised by helix

While frequency of attendance provides a baseline for measuring engagement, it does not capture the full picture. Additional factors, such as informal contacts, emails, regional meetings, and direct collaborations, are critical for understanding the broader scope of involvement. Furthermore, the nature of engagement often varies by stakeholder type.

Government stakeholders typically show lower event participation due to the nature of their responsibilities and decision-making processes, which are less reliant on frequent attendance

but more focused on strategic, policy-driven contributions. Nevertheless, two stakeholders from the Catalanian Government demonstrated noteworthy commitment: the Health Public Agency of Catalonia (ASPCAT) attended *three events*, and the Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú participated in *four events*.

Industry stakeholders demonstrated the highest presence in single events, reflecting their targeted interests and alignment with innovation and market needs. Their engagement, strongly connected to the Power-Interest Grid, reflects their interest in INTEGER's developments and results. Examples of medium engagement include Philips (Hamburg) participating in *three events*, AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster (Catalonia) in *five events*, Memima Baby (Catalonia) in *six events*, and Bax & Company, Healthy Cities (Catalonia) in *seven events*. Notably, the prominence of Catalanian stakeholders may reflect the advanced maturity of the regional ecosystem.

Academic organisations displayed a mix of low and high engagement. Most organisations participated in only one or two events, but the Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa (Catalonia) stands out with high attendance at *eight events*. Their consistent involvement likely reflects their close alignment with INTEGER's themes and objectives.

Civil society organisations showed lower levels of engagement overall, but the involvement of Senior Lab (Catalonia) in *five events* highlights its potential for more sustained participation. This organisation's interest in INTEGER stems from its aim to broaden its scope and business model, further evidenced by its involvement in mentorship sessions.

5. CONCLUSION

The INTEGER project has successfully engaged interregional and international stakeholders through **13 activities**, structured into **five main phases**: identifying challenges and needs, consulting on the 4H Model, engaging key players in the Col-laboratory, training and incubating, and celebrating milestones while ensuring sustainability.

Events connecting regions - Catalonia, Krakow, and Hamburg - proved particularly valuable, enabling stakeholders to exchange ideas, strategies, and approaches. However, during initial activities like the Key Stakeholder Pre-Event and Innovation 4Healthy Living events, it was noted that stakeholders first found it easier to connect with those from different sectors but within the same region. Nevertheless, Catalonian stakeholders, during the General Assembly, highlighted the value of inter-regional discussions, which facilitated learning from the diverse needs and engagement levels across regions.

Initiatives such as the OpenLivingLab Days, which had broad outreach and attracted many participants, were effective in disseminating the project. These efforts led to the collection of 26 Terms of Reference (ToR) signatures during the event. While 52 ToR signatures were secured overall, this figure may not fully reflect the extent of stakeholder engagement, as formal agreements may not resonate equally across all cultures.

Webinars and events involving international participants beyond the pilot regions highlighted the importance of dissemination through social media and partner networks. These activities brought in new stakeholders, including representatives from sister projects, who expressed interest in collaborative articles and bilateral meetings. Such events also introduced additional key players to the EU Col-laboratory, with two organisations signing the ToR despite not being previously involved.

The INTEGER training and incubation events, including the Col.laber training day and the two incubation sessions, were highly successful in transferring valuable knowledge for fostering healthy European innovation ecosystems. Due to the involvement of several external experts, participants gained valuable insights on topics like business model development, Social Return on Investment, and the use of social networks to promote social innovation. A key lesson learned was the importance of incorporating more time for practical exercises, such as case studies and video examples, to enhance hands-on learning. Additionally, the sessions could have allocated more time to the registration for theglocal.network to encourage participants to directly join and engage within the digital space. This could have supported more active collaboration between the stakeholders outside of the training sessions.

Of the **118 organisations** involved, **54** were from **industry**, **30** from **academia**, **19** from **government**, and **15** from **civil society**. Industry stakeholders formed the largest group, reflecting significant interest in the project from the quadruple helix, even if civil society participation was lower. However, lessons were learned and mitigation actions are being implemented, as a survey conducted by i2CAT that aims to provide insights into improving civil society engagement in future activities, among other issues.

In terms of participation within the interregional events, **58** organisations were based in **Catalonia** (3 from other parts of Spain), **7** in **Hamburg** (4 from other regions of Germany), and **11** in **Krakow** (4 from other areas of Poland). Additionally, **7** organisations had **unknown** origins,

2 were **European-wide**, **2** were **global**, and **20** came from **several countries** including Colombia, Turkey, Latvia, Portugal, Lithuania, Norway, Italy, Romania, and Estonia. Catalonia demonstrated high level of participation, with multiple institutions attending events. Meanwhile, participation from Krakow and Hamburg was comparatively lower, highlighting the need for more targeted outreach to engage local actors. These variations reflect the differing maturity levels of regional ecosystems and possibly varying familiarity with the Col-laboratory concept. Catalonia's early involvement and institutional support have driven stronger engagement, while Krakow and Hamburg may benefit from additional resources and focused attention.

Regarding the participation from the regions, it is important to note that this report has only looked at the coordination and collaboration activities from an interregional perspective, connecting the regions and stakeholders internationally. The content is strongly related to *Deliverable 4.4 - Report on coordination actions with key related initiatives*, which summarises the stakeholder coordination and involvement within the three INTEGER pilot sites, focusing on regional events.

In summary, the INTEGER project has fostered meaningful collaboration across regions and internationally, sharing knowledge on social innovation ecosystems and the 4H model. The consortium will continue meeting quarterly beyond the project's conclusion, aiming to establish a sustainable EU Col-laboratory to support regional and international cooperation, with the Decidim digital platform facilitating communication and collaboration.

6. FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

To ensure the project's long-term sustainability, key information and contacts will be transferred to the **Decidim** platform, as detailed in *Deliverable 5.3 – Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholders' Implementation Report*. Additionally, **i2CAT** has been gathering stakeholder feedback through a survey, supporting ongoing coordination and informing future actions.

A key lesson learned is the need for **more targeted communication and dissemination strategies** to effectively engage all 4H actors. Participation rates across the quadruple helix have varied, with industry consistently more engaged than other sectors. This highlights the importance of **tailored invitations** that align with the specific interests and incentives of each helix while also reinforcing the **benefits of interregional collaboration**.

A **more flexible programme** should be developed to encourage balanced participation, incorporating **varied formats** (online, onsite, and hybrid) and different session durations to accommodate diverse stakeholder needs. Enhancing monitoring tools and communication mechanisms, particularly through digital platforms or dedicated channels, may further strengthen engagement.

Regarding the **online platform**, dedicating time during events to introduce participants to its functionalities, demonstrate its benefits, and address questions in real-time could significantly **increase adoption and participation**. By refining these approaches, the project can ensure more inclusive engagement, foster cross-sector collaboration, and enhance its long-term impact.

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APPENDIX 1: INITIAL LIST OF SPECIFIC TARGET STAKEHOLDERS

The Consortium has compiled an initial list of specific target stakeholders within the categories defined in the Stakeholder analysis, and these are presented below. Each regional partner team was responsible for preparing a comprehensive stakeholders' map, starting with key stakeholders to participate in the first actions of the project.

The list was compiled through a mix of desk research and partner feedback and provided a starting point as the project commences for targeted communication. It has been reviewed as project progressed. The emails are kept internally for reasons of data protection.

Table 12 - Initial list of specific target stakeholders²

Krakow		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Government	National	The Polish Ministry of Health
	Regional	Marshall Office of Malopolska Region
	Local	Municipality Centre of Social Assistance
Civil Society	National	Polish National Initiative for Collaboration of Senior Councils
	Regional	Krakow Smog Alert
	Local	Senior Activity Centres
Industry	National	Polish Confederation Lewiatan
	Regional	Klaster Lifescience
	Local	DIABMED
Academia	National	Polish National Gerontological Association
	Regional	University of Science and technology Krakow
	Local	Faber Education Centre

² This list is just a sample of key stakeholders, none of the cases are exhaustive lists.

Hamburg		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Stakeholder
Government	Regional	Hamburg Ministry of Social Affairs
		Hamburg Ministry of Economy
		Hamburg Ministry of Science
Civil Society	Regional	Max und Ingeborg Herz Stiftung (Foundation)
		Patriotische Gesellschaft (Philanthropic civil society organisation)
Industry	National	Aidhere
		Philips
	Regional	Health Innovation Port
Academia	Regional	University Hospital Hamburg
		University Hamburg
		Hamburg University of Applied Science
Other	Regional	Hamburg Investment Bank
		Cluster Agency Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg GmbH
4Helix	Regional	Arbeitskreis nachhaltige Stadtgesundheit (transdisciplinary working group, Civil Society, Academia, Government, Economy)
Catalonia		
4 H areas	Level of impact	Type of Stakeholder
Government	Regional	Health department - Catalanian government
		Social & Family Department - Catalanian government
		Labour & Digital Societal Department- Catalanian government
Civil Society	Local	Patient Associations

		Consell Català de la gent gran
		Association of "AMPA" Mothers and fathers of primary schools
		Neighbourhood associations
Industry	Regional	Giromed Institute
		Me Mima Baby
	National	Bax & Company
		Eurecat
		Saluscoop
Academia	Regional	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
		Universitat Rovira i Virgili (URV)
		Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
		Universitat Barcelona (UB)
International Stakeholders		
4 H areas	Type of Stakeholder	
Government	DG Employment & Social inclusion	
Civil Society	Age platform Europe	
Industry	European Business & innovation Network	
	Phillips Health innovation port ; Gaia AG	
Academia	UNA Europa	
	NET4Age COST action	

APPENDIX 2: STAKEHOLDERS LISTS BY EVENT / PHASE

Table 6 - Names and number of organisations by helix in activities from “Identifying challenges and needs”

Helix		Organisation	Key stakeholder pre-event	Let's hack together! 1	Let's hack together! 2	Total	
Academia	Universities	- University Medical Department Hamburg (HAM)			X	3	
	Other research organisations	- Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa (CAT)	X	X	X		
		- Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili (CAT)	X	X			
Industry	Technology providers	- Phillips (HAM)	X			10	
	Business actors	- IFB Hamburg (HAM)	X				
		- Memima baby (CAT)	X	X			
		- Bax & Company (CAT)	X	X	X		
		- Giromed Institute (CAT)	X				
		- Prawnik (KRA)	X				
		- Fundacja Internationaler Bund Polska (KRA)	X				
		- Cracow. Instytut Wspomagania Wychowania (KRA)	X				
		- Sargim Foundation (before AEMA Foundation) (CAT)	X				
- Fundació Pere Tarrés (CAT)			X				
Civil society	Citizens, NGOs, and non-formal active groups	- SeniorLab (CAT)			X	1	
Government	Regulatory bodies	- EureCat Hub FoodTEch (CAT)	X			6	
		- Health Public Agency of Catalonia (CAT)	X	X	X		
	Public authorities	- Ajuntament de Vilanova i Geltrú (CAT)			X		X
		- Hospital San Joan de Deu (CAT)					X
		- Hospital Universitari Parc Tauli (CAT)			X		

		- Fundació Salut Empordà. Hosp Figueres (CAT)		X	X	
Total	Organisations (excluding INTEGER partners)		13	9	7	20
	Participants (including INTEGER partners)		39	23	18	-

Table 7 - Names and number of organisations by helix in activities from “Consulting on the 4H Model”

Helix		Organisations	Model Core Group 1	Model Core Group 2	Focus group	Total
Academia	Other research organisations	- Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa (CAT)	X	X	X	1
Industry	Technology providers	- Philips (HAM)	X	X		4
	Business actors	- Bax & Company (CAT)	X	X	X	
		- AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster (CAT)	X	X	X	
		- IFB Hamburg (HAM)			X	
Civil society	Citizens, NGOs, and non-formal active groups	- SeniorLab (CAT)	X		X	2
		- Marta (KRA)			X	
Government	Regulatory bodies	- Life Science Nord (HAM)			X	1
Total		Organisations (excluding INTEGER partners)	5	4	7	8
		Participants (including INTEGER partners)	15	13	16	-

Table 8 – Names and number of organisations by helix, in the Terms of Reference (ToR)

Helix		Organisation	ToR signatures	Tor signatures (Total)
Academy / research	Universities	- Valencian International University (CAT) - Living Lab Universidad de la Sabana (Colombia) - EKA University of Applied Sciences (Latvia) - Abdullah Gül University and Wellbeing Association (Turkey) - Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (CAT) - Aalborg University (Denmark) - Hatay Mustafa Kemal University (Turkey) - Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry Polish Academy of Sciences (Poland)	11	16

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fundació Universitària del Bages (CAT) - <i>Universitat Rovira i Virgili URV (INTEGER partner) (CAT)</i> - <i>Jagiellonian University (INTEGER partner) (KRA)</i> 		
	Other research organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aragonese Institute of Health Sciences (IACS) (CAT) - IrsiCaixa AIDS Research Institute (CAT) - Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili (CAT) - IDIAP JGol / ICS (CAT) - <i>i2CAT (INTEGER partner) (CAT)</i> 	5	
Industry	Technology providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Norway Health Tech (Norway) 	1	11
	Business actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AMBIT – Living Spaces Cluster (CAT) - Fundació Èpica Fura dels Baus (CAT) - Memima baby (CAT) - Suara Cooperativa (CAT) - Lithuanian Social Business Association (Lithuania) - Fonduri structurale (Romania) - Eoh-for-Good (SP) - <i>Krakov Technology Park (INTEGER partner) (KRA)</i> - <i>AFEdemy (INTEGER partner) (NL)</i> - <i>SHINE 2Europe (INTEGER partner) (PT)</i> - <i>F6S (INTEGER partner) (UK)</i> 	10	
Civil society	Citizens, NGOs, and non-formal active groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ideas for Change (CAT) - Sargim Foundation (before Fundación AEMA) (CAT) - Gruenhof e.V. (Germany) 	3	3
Government	Public authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Catalan Ministry of Health, Government of Catalonia (CAT) - Secretary of Telecommunications and Digital Transformation, Government of Catalonia (CAT) - Valls Genera (CAT) - Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú (CAT) - <i>Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs and Integration (INTEGER partner) (HAM)</i> 	5	7
	International networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European Network of Living Labs (EU) - European School of Social Innovation (EU) 	2	
Total	Organisations (including INTEGER partners)	38		
	Signatures	52		

Table 9 – Names and number of organisations by helix in the webinar

Helix		Organisation	Total
Academia	Universities	- IBCH PAS (KRA) - FCT NOVA - UCIBIO and Humanized Solutions (PT)	3
	Other research organisations	- Social Innovation Exchange (Global)	
Industry	Business actors	- Steinbeis Europa Zentrum (GER)	12
		- Project AHEAD (IT)	
		- Baltic Innovation Agency (EE)	
		- Epiguard (NO)	
		- Social Innovation Lab at Grünhof (GE)	
		- SHINE (PT)	
		- Fonduri Structurale (RO)	
		- AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster (CAT)	
		- YourY Network (Global)	
		- Trentino Social Tank (IT)	
		- Connecting Dots (LT)	
- Lithuanian Innovation Centre (LT)			
Civil society	Citizens, NGOs and non-formal active groups	- Norway Health Tech (NO)	4
		- ITA - Institut Català d'Antropologia (CAT)	
		- Kollektiva (EL)	
		- Lithuanian Social Business Association (LISBA) (LT)	
Total	Organisations		19
	Participants (including INTEGER partners)		32

Table 10 - Names and number of organisations by helix involved in activities related to the phase "Training and incubating"

Helix		Organisation	Final Col.laborat hon	Col.laber training day	How to sell with AI & LinkedIn	Im-perfect pitch	
Academy / research	Universities	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (CAT)		X			
		IT				X	
		Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NO)					X
		Medical University of Lodz (PL)		X			
		SWPS University (PL)		X			

		Warsaw University of Life Sciences (PL)		X		
	Other research organisations	Instituto Robotica (CAT)		X		
		Hub d'innovació social i sanitària - HiSS (CAT)		X		
		WeMind Cluster (CAT)				X
		Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa (CAT)		X		
		IDIAP JGol / ICS (CAT)				X
		CEI Torrefarrera (CAT)				X
		Sano - Centre for Computational Medicine (KRA)		X		
Industry	Technology providers	LEITAT Technological Center (CAT)		X		
	Business actors	Aufbruch.Hamburg (HAM)	X			
		help Mee Schmerztherapie GmbH (HAM)	X			
		Cónorex (CAT)	X			X
		Bax & Company (CAT)	X			
		t-valley ecosystem (CAT)		X		
		Qualitas Social Tech (CAT)		X		
		Memima baby (CAT)		X	X	
		Ship2B (CAT)	X	X		
		Hub4industry (KRA)			X	
		Autoemployed (CAT)			X	
		Csa (CAT)			X	
		Neapolis (CAT)			X	
		Talent Passport (CAT)			X	
		DoS (CAT)			X	
		Bee2be.tech (CAT)			X	
		Noupunt (CAT)			X	
		Bizmarketing (CAT)			X	
		ICS (CAT)			X	
		Free-lance (CAT)			X	
		Som essència sonora (CAT)			X	
	YASYT Tech & Knowledge (CAT)			X		
	ACG Coaching & Consulting (CAT)			X		
	Fondazione David Chiossone				X	
Didactiba				X		

Civil society	Citizens, NGOs, and non-formal active groups	ITA antropologia (CAT)		X		
		SeniorLab (CAT)			X	X
		Civel Society (CAT)			X	
		Fundacio iSocial (CAT)			X	
		Fundacja Brata Alberta (KRA)		X		
Government	Regulatory bodies	EureCat Hub FoodTEch (CAT)			X	
	Public authorities	Hamburgische Investitions- und Förderbank Hamburg (HAM)	X			
		BWI HH (HAM)	X			
		Ajuntament de Viladecans (CAT)		X		
		ConSORCI Sanitari de Terrassa (CAT)		X		
		Clúster TIC Sud (CAT)			X	
		Małopolska Regional Development Agency UMWM (KRA)		X		
		KLSK (KRA)	X			
	International networks	European School of Social Innovation (EU)		X		
Total	Number of organisations		8	19	22	7
	Participants (including INTEGER partners)		28	43	41	16

Table 11 - Names and number of organisations by helix in the co-creation part of the Final General Assembly

	Helix	Organisation	Total
Academy / research	Other research organisations	- Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CAT)	1
Industry	Business actors	- Memima baby (CAT) - Suara Cooperativa (CAT) - Ada Navarro (CAT)	3
Civil society	Citizens, NGOs, and non-formal active groups	- L'alzina (CAT) - Fundació Visible (CAT)	2
Government	Public authorities	- Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú (CAT) - VHIR (CAT)	2
Total	Organisations		8
	Participants (including INTEGER partners)		30

APPENDIX 3: Mural analysis of the webinar “ADVANCING TOGETHER: SHOWCASING SOCIAL INNOVATION INITIATIVES IN HEALTH AND WELLBEING”

Mural [Link](#)

Table 12 – Organised results from the co-creation part during the webinar

Current challenges <i>What are the main current challenges faced by your project?</i>	What do you need? <i>What are your project's needs?</i>	Who and what can help? <i>Who offers from other projects can support your project?</i>	Other ideas
<p>LACK OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND LACK OF OUTREACH</p> <p>Engaging new stakeholders/communities</p> <p>INTEGER: Interregional collaboration for local actors beyond partners</p> <p>CHES: Involving stakeholders in the workshops</p> <p>Invest4Health: Outreach to new testbeds/regions</p> <p>SIRENE: Outreach beyond “known” communities</p>	<p>INTEGER: Increase number of community members</p> <p>INTEGER: Free platform to move</p>	<p>SIRENE: Living community of experts on SHAFE, here</p> <p>IBESI: Gateway to Baltic SI Ecosystems as all partners have rich local networks, here</p> <p>Invest4Health: Knowledge of stakeholder and community engagement</p>	<p>Paper: Match-Funding as a Formula for Crowdfunding: a Case Study on the Goteo.org Platform</p> <p>Goteo.org</p>
	<p>POSITIVE: Build and strengthen local “mixed” innovation ecosystems and/or communities</p>	<p>INTEGER: Participatory online platform with new and different actors that could add value to other ones, here</p>	<p>Exploring how different innovation ecosystems create shared value: insights from a multiple case study analysis</p>

<p>Reaching specific communities</p> <p>IBESI: Finding a good model to interact with the investor community</p> <p>POSITIVE: Reaching the tech innovation ecosystem with our message</p> <p>Ensuring a win-win situation</p> <p>POSITIVE: building the role and a community of “digital ambassadors” inside social enterprises (at least in Trento)</p>	<p>Invest4Health: Connect with initiatives/projects with experience in social franchising</p>	<p>SIRENE: Living community of experts on SHAFE, here</p> <p>Invest4Health: Knowledge of stakeholder and community engagement</p> <p>CHES: Our experience working both at local levels with distinct socio-ecological challenges, while still connecting with other challenges in other regions</p>	<p>Investing in social franchising</p> <p>Social Impact clients</p>
	<p>Invest4Health: Connected with projects in the field of health and promotion and disease prevention as part of working group to share knowledge and learning</p>		<p>SHAFE Foundation</p> <p>Some projects where SHINE 2Europe (contact point: Inês Saavedra) works, including: LIVERATION, AI4HF</p> <p>Working group of Ageing - from Catalonia Col.laboratory (contact point: Rafel Nualart - i2CAT)</p>
<p>CHALLENGES ON SUSTAINING LONG-TERM ENGAGEMENT</p> <p>Maintaining stakeholder engagement over time</p>	<p>IBESI: Reflect on crowdfunding for SEs challenges</p>	<p>CONSOLID8: Knowledge on matchfunding/crowdfunding mechanisms</p>	<p>Match-Funding as a Formula for Crowdfunding: a Case Study on the Goteo.org Platform</p> <p>Goteo.org</p>

<p>INTEGER: Maintaining the community at mid/long-term</p> <p>IBESI: Maintaining the online community</p> <p>Invest4Health: Long-term stakeholder engagement and commitment</p> <p>Specific engagement needs</p> <p>IBESI: Maintaining SE interest in crowdfunding</p>	<p>IBESI: How to approach the investor community</p>		<p>InvestEU Portal</p>
<p>MAINSTREAMING AND REPLICATING RESULTS</p> <p>Mainstream project results</p> <p>CHES: How to involve policymakers at a later stage to mainstream the results</p>	<p>POSITIVE: Opportunities to disseminate and exploit results</p>	<p>INTEGER: Participatory online platform with new and different actors that could add value to other ones and possibility to add news, events, etc. Access here</p>	
<p>Replicating successful models</p> <p>POSITIVE: Transforming the successful POSITIVE Impact Challenge format in a long-term format in our regions</p>	<p>CHES: Opportunities to reach policymakers</p>	<p>SIRENE: Final event with strong attendance of policy makers (https://eventshafe.shine2.eu/)</p> <p>Invest4Health: Knowledge of novel and sustainable financing and business models for health promotion and disease prevention initiatives</p> <p>Invest4Health: Training programme for policy and decision makers on SCI</p>	<p>NET4Age-Friendly (Cost Action)</p>

		models and tools/ investment strategies to support Health Promotion and Disease Prevention initiatives	
<p>COMPARING RESULTS ACROSS ECOSYSTEMS</p> <p>CHES: Different levels of ecosystem consolidation - difficult sharing and comparing results of the workshops using the tools</p>	<p>IBESI: Best SI practices examples from the Nordics and rest of Europe</p> <p>SIRENE: Examples of good practices on social innovation</p> <p>SIRENE: Examples of projects/initiatives for the repository</p> <p>INTEGER: Examples of initiatives/tools for SI learning community</p>	<p>INTEGER: Training materials for col.laber (a manager for creating the conditions for social/business/technolog y-driven innovations to merge and for the quadruple helix actors to collaborate). Videopills + Col.laber's corner (in the INTEGER platform)</p> <p>POSITIVE: Sharing our learning on implementing UX Challenges for social organisations</p> <p>IBESI: Report on how our impact hackathon and accelerator were set up and the lessons learned</p> <p>CONSOLID8: Methodologies for running accelerators / capacity building programs</p> <p>SIRENE: Many inspirational and educational materials (inc. webinars, science cafes, videopills), here</p>	
<p>PROJECT SUSTAINABILITY</p>	<p>SIRENE: Follow-up initiatives as project approaches the end</p> <p>POSITIVE: Ideas on how to establish POSITIVE Impact Challenges as a long-term format (funding, sponsoring, etc.)</p>	<p>CONSOLID8: Knowledge on matchfunding/crowdfund ing mechanisms</p> <p>IBESI: Alternative finance roadmap</p>	<p>Match-Funding as a Formula for Crowdfunding: a Case Study on the Goteo.org Platform</p>

		<p>Invest4Health: Open call for additional regions/testbeds do simulation exercises with Smart Capacitating investment (SCI) methodology</p>	<p>Goteo.org</p> <p>European Innovation Ecosystems (it is possible to find funding opportunities there)</p>
	<p>CHES: Opportunity to continue working with ecosystems towards solutions building</p>		<p>INTEGER project aims to continue with its platform and some engagement work once the project finishes (in January). You can reach Rafel or Inês to understand what is being done in that regard.</p>
	<p>CHES: Unrestricted funding</p>		
	<p>CONSOLID8: Defining the roadmap post-implementation</p>		<p>How to create an effective project roadmap in 8 steps</p>

APPENDIX 4: Power-Interest Grid for interregional and/or international activities

Hear their opinions and implement them

Regulatory bodies

EureCat Hub FoodTEch (CAT)
Health Public Agency of Catalonia (ASPCAT)
Life Science Nord (GER)

Public authorities

Ajuntament de Viladecans (CAT)
Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú (CAT)
Catalan Ministry of health Government of Catalonia (CAT)
Consorci Sanitari de Terrassa (CAT)
Fundació Salut Empordà. Hosp Figueres (CAT)
Hamburgische Investitions- und Förderbank Hamburg (HAM)
Hospital Sant Joan de Deu (CAT)
Hospital Universitari Parc Tauli (CAT)
KLSK (KRA)
Małopolska Regional Development Agency UMWM (KRA)
Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs and Integration (HAM)
Secretary of telecommunications and digital transformation government of Catalonia (CAT)
Valls Genera (CAT)
VHIR (CAT)

Manage closely

Technology providers

Aragonese Institute of Health Sciences (SP)
LEITAT Technological Center (CAT)

Business actors

ACG Coaching & Consulting
Ada Navarro (CAT)
AFEdemy (NL)
AMBIT Living Spaces Cluster (CAT)
Aufbruch.Hamburg (HAM)
Autoemployed
Baltic Innovation Agency (EE)
Bax & Company. Healthy Cities (CAT)
Bee2be.tech
BizMarketing
BWI HH (HAM)
Clúster TIC Sud

Connecting Dots (LT)
Conorex Consulting (CAT)
Cracow. Instytut Wspomagania Wychowania (KRA)
Csa
Didactiba
DoS
Eoh-for-Good (SP)
EpiGuard (NO)
F6S (UK)
Fondazione David Chiossone
Fonduri Structurale (RO)
Free-lance
Fundació Èpica Fura dels Baus (CAT)
Fundacja Internationaler Bund Polska (KRA)
Giromed Institute (CAT)
Help Mee Schmerztherapie GmbH (HAM)
Hub4industry
ICS
IFB Hamburg (GER)
IVL Consulting (CAT)
Krakow Technology Park (KRA)
Lithuanian Innovation Centre (LT)
Memima baby (CAT)
Neapolis
Noupunt
Philips (GER)
Prawnik (KRA)
Project AHEAD (IT)
Qualitas Social Tech (CAT)
SHINE (PT)
Ship2B (CAT)
Social Innovation Lab at Grünhof (GE)
Som essència sonora
Steinbeis Europa Zentrum (GER)
Suara Cooperativa (CAT)
Talent Passport
Trentino Social Tank (IT)
t-valley ecosystem (CAT)
YASYT Tech & Knowledge
YourY Network (Global)

Monitor with a minimum effortResearch organisations

CEI Torrefarrera
Hub d'innovació social i sanitària - HiSS (CAT)
i2CAT (CAT)

IDIAP JGoI / ICS
Institut Català d'Investigació Química
Instituto Robotica (CAT)
IT
Living Lab de Salut d'IrsiCaixa (CAT)
Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili (CAT)
Sano - Centre for Computational Medicine (Krakow, PL)
Social Innovation Exchange (Global)
WeMind Cluster (CAT)

Universities

Aalborg University (Denmark)
Abdullah Gül University and Wellbeing Association (Turkey)
Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics -CED- (CAT)
EKA University of Applied Sciences (Latvia)
FCT NOVA - UCIBIO and Humanized Solutions (PT)
Fundació Universitària del Bages (CAT)
Hatay Mustafa Kemal University (Turkey)
IBCH PAS (KRA)
Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry Polish Academy of Sciences (Poland)
Jagiellonian University (KRA)
Living Lab Universidad de la Sabana (Colombia)
Medical University of Lodz (PL)
Norwegian University of Science and Technology
SWPS University (Warsaw, PL)
Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (CAT)
Universitat Rovira i Virgili URV (CAT)
Valencian International University (SP)
Warsaw University of Life Sciences (Warsaw, PL)

Keep informed about what the project has decided

International networks

ENOLL European Network of Living Labs (EU)
ESSI. European School of Social Innovation (EU)

Citizens, NGOs and non-formal active groups

Civil Society
Fundacio iSocial (CAT)
Fundació Pere Tarrés (CAT)
Fundació Visible (CAT)
Fundacja Brata Alberta (KRA)
Gruenhof e.V. (Germany)
ideas for Change (CAT)
ITA - Institut Català d'Antropologia (CAT)

Kollektiva (EL)

L'alzina (CAT)

Lithuanian Social Business Association (LISBA) (LT)

Marta

Norway Health Tech (NO)

Sargim Foundation (before AEMA Foundation) (CAT)

SeniorLab (CAT)